

GELMENTLAR AND THE DISEASES OCCURRING IN PEOPLE THAT PRODUCED THEM

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ABSTRACT

in today's world of men it is one of the most problematic issues with the incidence of gelmintozlar. Today in uzbekistan among the population, especially children at decisive, land-line for all the incidence of the condition with gelmintozlar lifemuch occurs. For this reason eithersh childrens inghaxsiy do not follow the rules of hygiene, wet fruit productsisee they make istemol without a good wash, good pishirilmagan sas sausage andiskalar bodies of the productistem that is the reason.

The actual ministry of the problem. In the world today, it is one of the most problematic issues with the incidence of gelmintozlar men. Today in uzbekistan among the population, especially among children, the incidence of the condition with a lot of gelmintozlar occurs. For this reason qilamasliklari young children follow the rules of personal hygiene, wet istemol products they make fruit without a good wash, good sausage and istemol pishirilmagan sas products that is the reason. 754 thousand of the total population in the country of 14 million worldwide, 43% consists of children and teenagers under the age of 18 accounted for. This indicator tends to occur in the country, while children and teenagers with our gelmintozlar increases that much more. For the same purpose today, with the incidence of children and teenagers in order to avoid that the gelmintozlar harmony in the areas of sanitary and epidemiological public health service staff has been carrying propaganda. Yuqi is suspected disease and diseases in the laboratory of parazitlar gelmintoz are obtained from those samples to check. In this regard, the calorie content depends on the position gigienik of the population health assessment and scientific base, water requirements to ensure that gigienik fits the criteria of improvement, to develop measures for ensuring the quality and safety of food products, food products, which consume the population, soil, water, air pollution level dynamics of many years of sanitary-gigienik aimed at reducing the negative effects of environmental factors and valuation of particular importance was further deepening research workers. Atrophic-factors of the environment may not be reflected in it is known to us that the various human health. In the meantime, the health of the population observed in the last decade of the harmful effects of the various factors associated with the deterioration of the environment is also recognized. In particular gelmintozlarni of getting infected soil, water, the meat of animals infected with the good disease gelmintoz pishirmasdan istemol to one of the main reasons is taking most of the complexity of the case. Gelmintozlar-parasitic

worms-helminth qo'zg'atadigan the sick. People mainly 2 types of helminth parasite in the body is flat and round worms). many of the following class helminth occurring in people to enter the teat or trematodes (Trematoda); or sestodalar lentasimon worms (Cestoda); nematodes or round worms (Nematodes).Gijja most common one among the people in today's day gelmintozlardan parasite.Mostly children, hunters, fishermen and their families, as well as yshovchi occurs in people in rural areas. A number of these and they live at the expense of human and in the development of parasitic plantsis justified and will increase.Gelmentlar-parasite tissue of the body of man and animals and tiny worms which live at the expense of the member –vomiting (helminth) in gelmintozlar the diseases that produced them is called. Gelmintozlar humanity is known from very ancient times, they make up 90 percent of all diseases parazitlar. The source of the disease the patient is vagijjalarbilan people infected animals. The type of the causative agent, contracting and contracting according to the way gelmintozlar is divided into three factors:type of larvae in times of crisis gijja invaziya biogelmintozlarbu diseases (infectious level) up to the stage boss yetilishidaoraliq a living organism –that is, you will need a biological environment.mGeogelmintozlarBu gelmintozda type larvae in the soil until reaching the infectious stage of the process is that the occurrence keladikontagiozkontagioz communication transmitted through gelmintozlar –the people directly to the people from this type of helminth dirty hands in his underwear, household items and supplies used in the wash the sheets through contracting. Diseases transmitted through the communication path to enterobioz gimenolepidoz and vomiting.This type of disease is common mainly among children. Gijja their eggs through feces contaminated with the external environment. Zararsizlantirilmagan incontinence and field crop irrigation with contaminated water hamdasabzavotlarning be also be used as fertilizer and berries creates a wide spread of this disease to the ground. Gijja also walk in the crop as a result of disease of dogs infected with oralab therefore, vegetables, berries and greens gijja is contaminated with eggs. Washed vegetables are not good people, they can become infected through the consumption of berries and greens gijja of the eggs themselves.Exactly, vegetables, berries and greens orqaliaskaridoz, trixotsefalyoz, ankilostomidoz, gijja come strongiloidoz vaexinokokkozokabi diseases.DardGijjalar has a toxic effect on the human body is too heavy complications you thought. Also, the reaction produces ularallergik. Reduces the body's ability to fight again against different infectious diseases. Mechanical damage to tissue and the vascular wall. The development of vitamins and mineral substances into the body assures people. They also have a large negative effect on the nervous system.Belgilarigijja anemia in patients suffering from the disease of the disease are weakness, fatigue, headache, pain in the abdominal area, nausea, nervousness, rash, allergic and skin spots appear to be different however, as clinical signs are observed. At the time of this sorrow full physical and cognitive development in young children remain behind of their treatment, the disease will cause serious complications such as epilepsy epileptic to come out of. You can make such a conclusion that, that is gelmintoz not only the individual member, but of the whole body severe debilitating symptoms appear when it is necessary to address to the doctor in his own time. To keep from yo'llarikasallikni than curing disease, its prevention is important. Strictly the rules of personal hygiene in the prevention of Gelmintozning must pass. Each person should be able to own means of personal hygiene. Before feeding, into the toilet to the door of tutqichlar ushlagach with soil upon the completion of the work and should wash hands

thoroughly with soap when it comes to children playing in the street. Also, short nails, it is necessary to get done. Polizda, at work in the garden of the hand to the mouth, you should keep away from. Especially, the negative habits like mouth hand often stick to young children in particular. Gijja eggs fruits-vegetables and greens have to wash in running water to prevent contracting through them. Put greens in salted water to soak before, and then washed in running water obdon, and then it is recommended to consume. Items remain in the care of children in preschool educational institutions at home and used at times it is necessary to pay attention and toys to keep them clean. Children tuvak, chairs, toys, medicines or disinfect the toilet and the threshold of the door must be cleaned thoroughly with boiling water every day. Gijja of eggs along with the dust in the air into the body through the respiratory tract and mouth in the room in order to avoid falling out of a job with regular wet cleaning, it is desirable to sprinkle water supirilishi the yard. Open water basins boil only water to drink, always well cooked and fried meat to consume is required.

Gelmintoz to refer to a specialist immediately when symptoms appear it is. Laboratory analysis on the basis of the filing of more appropriate and timely treatment uningnatijalari the course of the full implementation of the advice of the doctor with the patient's debilitating stood up quickly overcome this serious complication proceeds will cause you to go without. Conclusion. To conclude, we can say that the entire humanity is a parasite that gelmintozlar but dangerous for children and teenagers. This is caused by a number of studies in violation of parazitlarning entry into the human body will lead to. The best method of protection gelmintozlardan istemol to wash fruits and vegetables well outlined, open water just boil the drink of the water of the basin, is always well-cooked and fried meat to consume is required. In the present day to the younger generation up to be attentive to a healthy diet in their daily tea, vitamin should meet the needs of as possible. In each family the father-the mothers of these children and to their children to be attentive enough knowledge and skills to be able to chalinmasligi the diseases they should.

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